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Drona: The Practitioner of Injustice

Dr. G. Reghukumar¹

The truths behind laughter and scorn are sophisticated. As one dives deep into these truths, he attains a state of intense delight that dwells beyond the realm of words. The Mahabharata is an Indian Epic that offers rich scope for laughter, thought and philosophical exercise. There are multiple moments that induce thoughtful laughter in the work which transcend the stature of mere existence. Any attempt at the compilation of these moments would be futile as they constantly outgrow the bounds leading one to fresher ones, offering scope many a time for umpteen research attempts. The present paper aspires to interpret one such series of scornful laughter in The Mahabharata.

“Yadihāsti tad anyatra / Yannehāsti na kutrachit.” One does not need another sloka to make a statement on this epic. The idea could be summarised as follows: One may find the things stated in this elsewhere too; but that which is not in this will not be seen anywhere else in the world. The excellence shown by the author of this epic to represent minutely the working of the mind of man, elevates him almost to the stature of the Divine creator. The brilliance of the epic even compels some literary historians to doubt whether this has been crafted by a single author. “To study Mahabharata would mean studying the life of Man and his relations, the dilemmas roused by those relations, and to study those minds that winnow these dilemmas” (Thomas 114).

As the brilliant Malayalam writer Anand observes: “The work of the epic is to sow the seeds. To grow trees from it is the duty of the farmers with imagination” (Anand 115). Based on the story and characters of this epic, The Mahabharata, thousands of creative works have already

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come out in various languages and the process is still on. A remarkable fact of The Mahabharata is that it is a cornucopia with immensely rich meaning and interpretive possibilities. When Anand opines that epics have sown the seeds of writing forever, the view of Thomas Mathew on the possibility of the re-narration of the epic tale too could be taken: “Epics, which are the creative result of the awareness of life and living assimilated by a people through the ages, have at each phase of civilization unceasingly released resonating voices of new meanings and new relevance” (Mathew 84).

V. S. Khandekar’s *Yayāti*, Sivaji Sawant’s *Karna*, M. T. Vasudevan Nair’s *Randāmoozham* all form part of the continuum to be traced back to Sree Harsha, Bhāsa, Kalidāsa and others. Though centuries have rolled on after the birth of the epics, mankind seems to have failed to realise the merit of the stories and the characters as depicted by the author of the source text. When proper interpretation itself has not happened, what can one say of re-interpretation! One of the best instances to be cited is the story of Dronācharya in Mahābharata. Vyāsa with his awareness of noble values hails Dharmaputra as the excellent mortal. There were many excelling him in skills and smartness. But the poet Vyasa subtly points out the flaws in them. We readers have not yet clearly distinguished them from the excellent qualities possessed by Dharmaputra.

An attempt is made here to approach the story of Drona as narrated in the source text. The paper aspires to mitigate the misunderstanding related to the character through this approach, attempted without any prejudice or reservation regarding the greatness of Drona as attributed to him.

Rishi Bharadwāja was one of the disciples of Rishi Valmiki. He was with Valmiki when the savage hunter killed one of the Krauncha birds with an arrow. Bharadwāja meets Khritāchi, the heavenly beauty (Apsaras) on the shores of River Ganga. The moment the Apsaras sees the Rishi, she tries to flee from there but her garment gets caught in a bush and drops down. Though it is the Apsaras who go naked, on closer analysis it becomes clear that it is Bharadwāja who is insulted. The birth of one of the greatest names in The Mahabharata, Drona, thus happens at this juncture.

In presenting Drona, the hero who had seen the other shore of weapon and martial arts, with the accompaniment of a mocking smile has a logic in the figurative text of The Mahabharata. The essence of sarcasm that spreads, and grows up to the Kurukshetra war could very well be read through the story of Drona. Furtive intentions and selfishness could be perceived in all the deeds of Drona presented in the tale. “Karmanyevādhikarasthe/ Mā bhaleshu kadāchana” goes the saying. But no deed of Drona is devoid of intentions as he always has his secret agenda up his sleeves.

Acquisition of both knowledge and the revered position of the Guru

Coming to know that Parasurama was giving away all that belonged to him, Drona reaches there to acquire Dhanurveda. His next desire was to earn brilliant disciples. He reaches Hastinapuri in disguise, and stays at Sage Gautama’s ashrama, to gain Kauravas and Pandavas as his disciples. His intention was to attract Kauravas and others with his prowess in weapon art and warfare. While the Kuru princes were playing, their toy, a ball, fell into the nearby well. Drona who reached there snatched this opportunity and threw his ring into the well. He promised to retrieve the two if they promise to offer lunch to him and easily takes the two making use of blades of grass as his arrows. Drona apprises the Kuru princes of their poor skills in weapon art. When the children ask him as to what he would have in return, he demands the children to merely inform Bheeshma of how a dark-skinned, short-statured man had helped them retrieve the ball from the well. Bheeshma invites Drona to the palace and adorns him as the Guru of the Kuru Princes in Dhanurvedya. Here again, one witnesses the fulfilment of Drona’s secret intentions. He does not adopt the straightforward path of revealing his desires. Despite possessing excellent skills in many disciplines including weapon arts and combat, Drona who adopts counterfeit means becomes fit to be disdained.

Lessons of Injustice

Drona never exudes the qualities expected of a genuine Guru (master), right from the teaching of weapon art. He tries to teach certain techniques only to his son, Aswadhāma. Arjuna, who grows suspicious of the Guru’s act of giving special lessons to Aswadhāma after sending all the other students to draw water from the well,

starts coming back first after drawing water. As a Guru, he becomes compelled to teach the techniques to Arjuna too. Noticing Arjuna's extraordinary intellectual abilities, Drona instructs the cook secretly not to serve the food to Arjuna in the dark. Drona feared that once Arjuna eats in the dark, and realises the possibility of using the hand adeptly even in the dark, he might teach himself and gain experience on his own in driving the arrow to the desired end, keeping his eyes shut. But once the lamp got blown out in the wind while the children were having their dinner. While all the others waited for the lamp to be lit again, Arjuna alone ate and learned that with regular training one could earn the skill of driving the arrow straight to a spot without constantly gazing at the spot. On realising the extraordinary talent and potential of Arjuna, Drona embraces him with immense happiness and promises that he as Arjuna's Guru would prevent anyone else from becoming his equal in archery.

This is the third scene of scorn and disdain painted by the writer of the epic. The heart of Drona gets caught in the wrong kind of anxiety. Finally, what he was scared of happens. At this juncture again it is not the greatness of a Guru that is witnessed but mean and partiality-driven words emanate from Drona. Will Vyasa ever deem such a Guru in the noble and virtuous lineage of great masters like Sandeepani?

Now comes the fourth scene of laughter. Though Drona was crafty and skilled he did not have anything with him to even buy milk for his child. Once Ashwathāma's friends gave a drink made of rice flour to him, fooling him to consume it as milk. Any father would be pained at such a happening. But the way Drona's mind works at such an instance could be analysed closely. Acharya's mind immediately recollects the promise given to him by the child Drupada, who was his friend in the gurukula. The child Drupada had fondly told him that if at all Drona turned out to be poor and he had by then become a king, Drona should come to him for half of the kingdom. Being reminded of this long-lost promise, Drona goes with his wife and son to King Drupada's palace. Drupada insults him. The insulted Drona returns home but stacks his vengeance towards Drupada in his mind. The mean Drona goes to the extent of demanding a strange 'Gurudakshina' (token of respect and gratitude shown to the master) later from his disciples

– to tie Drupada up and to bring him to his presence. Drona thus becomes a shameless Guru who manipulates his disciples to forward his vengeance. Arjuna fulfils the desire of his Guru and Drona accepts the kingdom of Pāncāla. Who would not be spurred to scorn and laugh at the selfish designs of the great ‘Guru Drona’?

Drona’s vicious actions do not cease even at this juncture. Once when Drona ventures into the forest with his disciples, their dog starts barking at Ekalavya, the son of a savage. The great archer Ekalavya sends seven arrows to bind the dog’s mouth. When the dog returns to the princess with seven arrows around his mouth Arjuna is dumbfounded.

Ekalavya had approached Drona earlier requesting him to be made a disciple. But being the son of a barbarian, a Nishada, he is denied access by Drona. Disappointed, Ekalavya returns to the forest, makes an idol of Drona out of clay, prays to the idol and carries on his self-study of the art of using weapons. Now he has become even better than Arjuna as an archer.

When Arjuna brings Ekalavya’s matter to Drona’s attention, he unashamedly approaches Ekalavya and begs his thumb as ‘Gurudakshina’. The famous novelist Anand writes on this shameless act – “Now take the story of Drona. Drona had become Ekalavya’s Guru without his own knowledge and without any hard work. Still accepting the position of the Guru attributed by Ekalavya to him, he misuses that sacred position of the Guru to destroy the ‘vidya’ or skill and knowledge in his disciple, instead of honouring the position of the Guru. Look at how he mocks and insults ‘vidya’ and the source of vidya which is the ‘Gurusthana’(the space of the master). And what is the reason? To protect the arrogance of his dear disciple and prince, Arjuna, as the greatest archer in the world” (14). Was not Drona practising injustice to the core? In the battle at Kurukshetra too Drona’s role was not a respectable one.

Drona cheated his favourite disciple as well. For mere material benefit, like a hired soldier, again belittling his skill and knowledge he becomes willing to sell his skills to the Kauravas for whom he had no regard. Yet this man is regarded as the owner of the greatest of knowledge in The Mahabharata. The zenith of weapon art. The

greatest of the great. (Anand 14). The most desired skill and knowledge accomplished through great penance is torn off by Ekalavya drawing an arrow from his quiver when he sees Drona gazing at him asking for his hard-earned vidya as ‘Gurudakshina’.

The unpardonable stance adopted by Drona is seen justified by some critics like Thuravoor Vishwambharan. Drona is whitewashed by the critic. That Ekalavya is a ‘Nishada’ (savage) cannot be helped by Drona. The other disciples of Drona are not in favour of learning alongside a ‘Nishada’. Drona cannot be blamed for that either. The Acharya Drona has not revealed to anyone the logic of training a ‘Nishada’ too as a disciple. As a clan the ‘Nishadas’ usually engage in sinful deeds. Hence their lifestyle would be distinctly different from that of the mainstream population. These are offered as explanations to whitewash the actions of Dronacharya. Ekalavya was paying obeisance to the idol of Drona though he was learning himself. He was misusing the name of Drona without his consent. He was also propagating the news that he was Drona’s disciple and felt proud of that. In fact, this was a great mistake. To cut the arguments short, Thuravoor Vishwambaran justifies the ‘Gurudakshina’ that Drona receives from Ekalavya, the gift of his valuable thumb. The partiality and discrimination practised since his birth by Drona is not paid any heed to by the scholar.

This sort of a justification does not seem to be expected by Vyasa. Vyasa who raises only Dharmaputra to the high pedestal of all Dharma and virtues does not abstain from pointing out the flaws and limitations of the other Acharyas. It is here that the epic writer’s greatness as a poet glows tremendously.

Conclusion

As one peruses the mind, words and deeds of Dronacharya of The Mahabharata fame one realises that Drona is an abject failure.

1. It is with a secret agenda that Drona acquires knowledge and his disciples
2. Drona metes out differential treatment to his son and his other disciples. Not only does he not try to deal ideally with Arjuna’s arrogance but waters it with his attitude.
3. He scorns Ekalavya, the one who comes seeking knowledge.
4. Had he been a great guru he would not have been anxious

- about Arjuna's curiosity.
5. He deploys his 'Gurudakshina' to finish off his enemies.
 6. He receives from Ekalavya the most undeserving and spiteful of 'Gurudakshinas'.
 7. Even in the battlefield at Kurukshetra he does not adopt a fair and just stance.
 8. Though a great scholar, he was a Guru (master) without a dignified culture.

The epic writer with a profound scorn and smile deploys such a master for granting the Kauravas and the Pandavas training in martial arts with clear farsightedness. The Guru should carry within him the light of culture, in the absence of which all that one acquires would be deployed for total destruction. Vyāsa, the one deemed to be the epic writer, with a smile states exactly that without making an explicit statement, through the story of Drona as to who a Guru is and what he should be. Without realising this fact, we have even instituted an award in his name.

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